

METHODOLOGY OF CREATING A NEW GENERATION OF EDUCATIONAL LITERATURE FROM THE SCIENCES OF ENGINEERING GRAPHICS

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Annotation: The term "electronic textbook" is currently firmly established in the field of education, but there is still no unified point of view among scientists regarding the essence of this concept. This has led to the appearance of synonymous terms such as "electronic publication of the learning objective", "curriculum", "e-learning tool", "computer training program", "computer learning tool" and others. It has been. In addition to the mentioned problem, it can be noted that even if the term "electronic textbook" itself is recognized, there is no agreement among teachers on the definition of this concept. Based on the analysis of scientific-methodical literature, it became known that the addition of a feature such as "electronic" to the term "textbook" began to be used in connection with the emergence of computers in education, and as a result, the potential of computers to present information in a new - electronic form increased.

In the master's thesis, the creation of new generation educational and methodical literature in engineering graphics was considered as an urgent issue.

Key words: new generation, electronic textbook, engineering, art, development, student, teacher, pedagogy.

Аннотация: Термин «электронный учебник» в настоящее время прочно утвердился в сфере образования, однако до сих пор среди ученых нет единой точки зрения относительно сущности этого понятия. Это привело к появлению синонимичных терминов, таких как «электронное издание цели обучения», «учебный план», «электронное средство обучения», «компьютерная учебная программа», «компьютерное средство обучения» и др. Это произошло. В дополнение к указанной проблеме можно отметить, что даже при признании

самого термина «электронный учебник» среди учителей нет единого мнения по поводу определения этого понятия. На основе анализа научно-методической литературы стало известно, что добавление к термину «учебник» такого признака, как «электронный», стало использоваться в связи с появлением компьютеров в образовании, и, как следствие, возросли возможности компьютеров по представлению информации в новой - электронной форме.

В магистерской диссертации актуальным вопросом считалось создание учебно-методической литературы нового поколения по инженерной графике.

Ключевые слова: новое поколение, электронный учебник, техника, искусство, развитие, ученик, учитель, педагогика.

The term "electronic textbook" is now firmly established in the field of education, but even now there is no unified point of view among scientists regarding the essence of this concept. This has led to the appearance of synonymous terms such as "electronic publication of the learning objective", "curriculum", "e-learning tool", "computer training program", "computer learning tool" and others. it has been. In addition to the indicated problem, it can be noted that even if the term "electronic textbook" itself is recognized, there is no agreement among teachers on the definition of this concept. [Page 1, 5.].

Based on the analysis of scientific-methodical literature, it became known that the addition of a feature such as "electronic" to the term "textbook" began to be used in connection with the appearance of computers in education, and as a result, the potential of computers to present information in a new - electronic form increased.

Effective organization of the teaching-learning process in the modern ICT environment. The subject of electronic pedagogy is the pedagogical system. Pedagogical system includes the following components: teacher, student, goals and tasks of education, content of education, forms, methods and tools of education. Modern ICT contributes to all these components.

Taking into account the principles that must be followed when creating an electronic textbook (quantization, completeness, visualization, network, control, adaptation, computer

support, stackability), the design of the technology of creating an electronic textbook includes 7 stages gets:

- 1) development of the concept (development of the main idea of creating an electronic textbook based on the science standard and training methodology, creating a meaningful part of the textbook);
- 2) designing (developing a working example, a set of templates of information blocks and screen forms, an orderly scheme of the structure of hyperapplications ensuring the interactivity of references);
- 3) design of screen form and information blocks (construction of a design structure in accordance with the specific educational process, psychological-pedagogical features, ergonomic requirements, structure and content of educational materials);
- 4) prepare educational materials in electronic form and divide them into elementary parts-modules designed for one work session, i.e. one lesson;
- 5) filling in the elements of the application structure (placing the prepared materials on the developed templates and screen forms, filling in the application system and organizing feedback with the user);
- 6) testing and tuning (checking the correctness of each application, communication work and the correctness of the program's response to user actions);
- 7) implementation in the educational process (of course, the use of electronic textbooks in general secondary schools with the collection of data on the reflection of teachers and students).

Education in the modern ICT environment cannot be imagined without the use of Internet resources. The Internet has a huge potential for educational services. E-mail, virtual library and museums, educational portals and sites, thematic blogs and forums, teleconferences, electronic olympiads and quizzes are becoming a component of modern education. It creates wide opportunities for using these educational services, both in class and extracurricular activities. The use of Internet educational resources encourages the teacher to become a manager of the educational process.

The creation of educational electronic tools ensures the interdependence of the following three important stages:

- Content stage - at this stage, the formation of information and educational resources of electronic means and the content of its information supply is created;
- Organizational stage - at this stage, in addition to the technical aspects of creating electronic tools, clarification of categories of users, development of mechanisms for systematization and updating of existing resources, integration of existing resources in educational institutions, organization of electronic education, information-educational resources collection and analysis of statistical data on users in order to determine the demand;
- Stage of methodical support - at this stage, the development of the methodology of using electronic tools in the educational process, and the implementation of consulting services are started.

Adabiyotlar ro‘yxati:

1. Балалаева Е.Ю. Анализ сущности понятия «Электронный учебник» // Вестник Марийского государственного университета. – 2016. – №4 (24). – С. 5-9.
2. Овчинникова К.Р. Учебник и электронный учебник: исторический экскурс // Сибирский педагогический журнал. – 2007. – №8. – С. 292-305.
3. Уваров А.Ю. Электронный учебник: теория и практика / А.Ю. Уваров. – М.: Изд-во УРАО, 1999. – 220 с.
4. Крук Б.И., Журавлева О.Б. Электронный учебник как средство субъектно-объектного инфовзаимодействия в процессе обучения: проблемы инфовзаимодействия / Б. И. Крук, О. Б. Журавлева, И. В. Калачев. – Новосибирск. – Вып. 2. – 2000. – 189 с..
5. Сысоева С.А. Создание и внедрение электронных учебных средств: теоретический анализ проблемы (часть I) // Непрерывное образование. – 2005. – № 1-2. – С.78-85.
6. Ахмедова А.М. Использование современных электронных средств обучения в учебном процессе // Science Time. Выпуск. – 2015. – № 1 (13). – С. 36-39.

7. Батищев В.И., Мишин В.Ю. Мультимедийные средства обучения // Сборник материалов конференции «Единая образовательная информационная среда: проблемы и пути развития». – 2003. – [Электронный ресурс]. URL: <http://dist.knteu.kiev.ua/files/metod5.pdf>

8. Новые педагогические и информационные технологии в системе образования : учебное пособие для студентов вузов [Текст] / под ред. Е. С. Полат. – 3-е изд., испр. и доп. – Москва : Академия, 2008. – 269 с.

9. Тыщенко О.Б. Новое средство компьютерного обучения – электронный учебник // Компьютеры в учебном процессе. – 1999. – № 10. – С. 89–92.